

THE ROLE OF ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL ECONOMY INDICATORS

Safarova Dilshodaxon Eshmuxammadovna

Fergana State University, doctoral student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8058595>

Abstract: In the article, technological changes specific to the digital economy, the impact of the development of the digital economy on employment, the creation of a national digital economic system, the share of ICT in GDP, the analysis of some indicators of communication and information, the number of special software, used in this area.

Key words: digital economy, development of digital economy, national digital economic security, software tools, country's economic indicators.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, every country considers the development of the digital economy as its priority. With the help of state programs, digitization, security and legal regulation, the level of digital literacy in our country is being analyzed and developed. Uzbekistan is also increasing the pace of adaptation to the process of developing the digital economy. As a result of the reforms implemented in the new Uzbekistan, openness, the development of international economic and political relations have created opportunities for the modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of industrial sectors in our country. An example of this is the increase in the volume of foreign trade of our country. Hundreds of expressions such as "electronic government", "electronic management", "telecommunications", "internet", "website" have become an integral part of our life. IT covers every aspect of our daily life.

METHODOLOGY

Economic statistical indicators of the development of the digital economy in our country were analyzed. The activities of the digital economy were closely studied and a database was compiled. Based on the collected data, methods such as observation and comparison of economic analysis, systematic approach and logical approach were effectively used.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

As a result of the ongoing reforms, 178 services have been launched through the Electronic Government and the unified interactive services portal, and these services are saving citizens' time and costs. We know very well that the creation of a digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and labor resources. Therefore, active transition to the digital economy will be one of our top priorities in the next 5 years. Digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services, but also dramatically reduce excess costs, especially corruption.

Here, let's focus on the concept of digital economy. It is the optimization of the interrelated production, distribution, exchange, consumption and management processes (inter-human, inter-machine, clouds and big data) by means of digital technologies and the Internet. is a for-profit activity.

At this point, it should be noted that the foundations of a new renaissance period - the third Renaissance - are being laid, which shows the greatness of our perspective. It is difficult to imagine the development of society and country without knowledge and enlightenment.

In particular, digital literacy has become an indispensable requirement for every citizen to communicate in the modern world, to find a job, to receive a comprehensive education or to teach. Having the right and complete set of digital skills is essential not only to succeed in today's world, but also to become more open, inclusive and safer.

Digital literacy is both a global and a local issue. Countries and regions require tailored approaches to meet their unique needs. Some governments are making strategic plans to improve citizens' digital literacy, albeit with different goals. For example, the Republic of Korea prioritized the development of digital skills in public administration officials to improve the efficiency of public services. At the same time, Oman has used Microsoft's digital literacy curriculum to improve its ICT workforce and prepare young people for employment. In 2019, the Ukrainian government launched a national digital education platform called Dia Digital Education, which offers more than 75 courses and educational materials to its citizens. Through its Skills Agenda, the EU aims to ensure that 70% of adults have basic digital skills by 2025 and to reduce the proportion of teenagers with low scores in numeracy and digital literacy from 30% in 2019 to 15% by 2030. Ghana has partnered with the World Bank's Digital Economy for Africa initiative to launch the US\$212 million eTransform program to provide training, mentoring and access to technology.

Specific quantitative indicators for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan have also been established, covering the period from 2020 to 2023. In particular, in 2020-2021, connecting all healthcare institutions, schools and preschool organizations, as well as villages and neighborhoods to a high-speed Internet network, and improving the quality of communication services, fully modernizing digital infrastructure and modern telecommunication services in all regions predicting the possibility of use, by 2022, the share of electronic government services will reach 60 percent, and by 2023, the share of the digital economy in the country's gross domestic product will be doubled.

The results of practical efforts did not take long. According to the results of June 2020, "Speedtest Global Index" published new data, and in the internet speed rating, Uzbekistan currently occupies the 94th place, an increase of 36 places in a year. observed. In general, the speed of wired internet in Uzbekistan increased by 2.5 times in the last year.

In order for us to join the ranks of developed countries, first of all, it is necessary to take the shortest path to advancement by acquiring knowledge in the field of advanced modern information and communication, Internet and digital technologies.

After all, according to our geographical location, we have to cross at least two borders in order to reach the ports of large water bodies by land. This has a negative impact on our position in the world market, both in terms of time and economically. The solution to this directly depends on intelligence, new innovations and the potential of qualified personnel.

Another important aspect is digitization of the sectors that the population is facing the most in our country, priority is being given to easing people's burden. In particular, the practical processes of digitalization of healthcare, cadastre, social protection, agriculture, and education have started and will soon bring positive results.

The digital economy will bring about certain changes in society, in particular, its impact on working conditions will be significant. In the conditions of digital transformation, the

increase in automation processes, artificial intelligence, analytical systems working with huge data, and the increase in the use of robots serve as substitutes for labor resources. As a result, business conditions improve and efficiency increases significantly.

The most important thing in the purposeful introduction of digitization technologies into our daily life is that interactive communication with the people is accelerating by offering government services to the population. This also shows that it is the right way to further expand the system of providing electronic public services to the population and business entities based on the principles of "intellectual government".

Naturally, these situations can be positively evaluated and recognized. Because the digitization programs implemented by our state allow us to correctly understand the wishes of our people and, moreover, our entrepreneurs. Naturally, these programs should be further expanded and improved. However, there are some problems that need to be solved in a short time.

First, digitization is a "data warehouse," a vast amount of data. Secondly, it is important for us to expand the various platforms to manage, store and process the flow of "big data". Thirdly, although the implementation mechanisms and sources of financing are indicated in the estimation of the implementation of these programs, we believe that it is important to strengthen public control during the monitoring process.

The results of the World Bank study entitled "Digital Dividends" show how relevant and important the digital economy is in the development of countries' economies. In particular, a 10% increase in internet speed will lead to an increase in the country's GDP. In developed countries, this indicator is 1.21 percent, while in developing countries it is 1.38 percent. So, if the Internet speed doubles, it is possible to increase the GDP by almost 15%.

In countries with a developed digital economy, both the volume of GDP and the share of GDP per capita are high. In this regard, the attention of the head of our state to this issue at the state level has one goal, which is, firstly, to raise the standard of living of the population, and secondly, to increase the real income of the population.

On April 28, 2020, the President of Uzbekistan signed Resolution No. 4699 on "Measures for Widespread Implementation of Digital Economy and Electronic Government"¹. By 2023, it is planned to double the share of the digital economy in the GDP of Uzbekistan, and to increase the number of electronic public services to 376 (currently, the provision of 326 public services through the single interactive public services portal (YIDXP) has been launched [2]).

The decision also envisages the development of digital entrepreneurship by increasing the volume of services in this field by 3 times and increasing their export to 100 million dollars by 2023. Also, the opening of digital literacy training centers in all regions in 2022 is considered noteworthy.

In addition, by the Decree of the President No. 6079 of October 5, 2020, the national strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" was approved, and the share of the digital economy in GDP in 2030 is 30 percent, and the target indicators for the development of digitalization in it. It is covered in more detail in the regional section.

According to the UNCTAD digital economy report published in 2019, 7 digital companies (Microsoft, Apple, Amazon, Google, Facebook, Alibaba and Tencent) accounted for 3/2 of the total global market capitalization. About 40 percent of the added value created in the field of

global information and communication technologies is accounted for by the United States and China.

As of 2021, the share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product of Uzbekistan was 1.6 percent, 9.3 percent in the United States, 3.8 percent in China, and 8 percent in India [3].

The amount of gross added value created in the fields of information economy and electronic commerce of our republic can be seen in the data of Table 1 includes the sale of products (goods, works and services) using trading platforms). According to it, the volume of gross added value in the information economy and e-commerce sector in 2019 was 8,491.9 billion soums, 86.2 percent of which was allocated to the information and communication technologies (ICT) sector, 10.7 percent to the content sector and to mass media, 3.1 percent to e-commerce.

In 2020, the volume of gross added value in the information economy and electronic commerce sector was 10,777.0 billion soums, 84.4 percent of which was allocated to the information and communication technologies (ICT) sector, and 10.1 percent to the content sector and mass media, 5.5 percent corresponded to e-commerce. We can see from this that the volume of gross added value created in the field of e-commerce in our country has increased by 331.4 billion soums compared to 2019.

By 2021, the gross added value in the information economy and e-commerce sector will be 17,066.5 billion soums, 68.5 percent of which will be allocated to the information and communication technologies (ICT) sector, and 8.6 percent to the content sector and mass media, 22.9 percent corresponded to e-commerce, that is, it amounted to 3,907.3 billion soums. From this indicator, we can see that in 2021, compared to 2019, the volume of gross added value created in the field of e-commerce in our country increased by 3647.3 billion soums.

Table 1

The volume of gross added value created in the fields of information economy and e-commerce [6].

Indicators	2019		2020		2021	
	billion soums	%	billion soums	%	billion soums	%
"Sector of information economy and e-commerce"	8 491,9	100,0	10 777,0	100,0	17 066,5	100,0
Sector of information and communication technologies (ICT)	7 323,0	86,2	9 095,9	84,4	11 694,6	68,5
ICT production	279,4	3,8	540,1	5,9	630,3	5,4
ICT trade	293,3	4,0	252,3	2,8	367,8	3,1
ICT services	6 750,3	92,2	8 303,5	91,3	10 696,4	91,5
Content sector and Mass media	908,9	10,7	1 089,7	10,1	1 464,6	8,6
E-commerce	260,0	3,1	591,4	5,5	3 907,3	22,9

By 2025, the world's digital economy will reach 23 trillion US dollars. Its share in the world gross domestic product will increase from the current 17.1 percent to 24.3 percent. 100 billion connections will be made worldwide to drive digital transformation in utilities, industry and agriculture, transportation, finance and more. The number of enterprises using cloud technologies is 85%, artificial intelligence - 86%, digital big data - 80%.

The digital economy operating on information technology platforms is developing rapidly, which requires the creation of new models and technologies for such platforms. These are the conductive (complex) technologies of the digital economy:

1. Big Data technologies;
2. Internet technologies (IoT - Internet of Things);
3. Mobile technologies;
4. Cloud technologies (Cloud computing);
5. Virtual and augmented technologies (VR - virtual reality) (AR - augmented reality);
6. Neurotechnologies and artificial intelligence (AI);
7. Digital platforms;
8. Quantum technologies;
9. Robotics;
10. Blockchain and cryptocurrency technologies;
11. Crowdsourcing and crowdfunding.

The introduction of the digital economy into the real sector of the economy serves to form technical and technological competences, which requires the establishment of expert support centers for scientific research and development, as well as their commercialization. Thus, the practice of forming the "Digital Economy" shows that its impact on economic processes is multifaceted, and this impact is stable and permeates all spheres of society, state and population's life [4].

Undoubtedly, the digital economy is the future. The competitiveness of the national economy depends to a large extent on how quickly we decide to adapt to the Industrial 4.0 revolution, which is considered an important component of the digital economy, and introduce digital technologies to all sectors of the economy. Effective organization of work in this area depends on mature personnel with sufficient competencies in the field of digital technologies. It should be noted that systematic measures have been taken in this regard.

In particular, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development is tasked with opening at least 100 training centers for digital technologies in all regions. It is planned to organize short-term training courses in such areas as the basics of programming, e-commerce and graphic design. In addition, it is planned to open special departments on blockchain technologies in the leading higher education institutions of the republic.

The adoption of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 17, 2021 "On measures to create conditions for the rapid introduction of artificial intelligence technologies" is a necessary condition for the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies in economic sectors and sectors in our country. was an important step to create conditions.

In accordance with this decision, the important aspects of the introduction of artificial intelligence - the legal regime, institutional frameworks, personnel training and qualification,

international and national standards, priority areas and sectors for the introduction of artificial intelligence, development of international cooperation are covered.

It should be noted that agriculture, banking, finance and tax, transport, energy, healthcare, pharmaceuticals, and e-government are the priority industries and sectors for the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies in our country.

It is worth noting that today there is a fierce competition for the development of artificial intelligence and investment in this field at the global level. The People's Republic of China is a clear leader in artificial intelligence research. By 2030, the value created by artificial intelligence is expected to reach 150 billion US dollars. Also, the USA, Great Britain, Canada, Russia, Germany, Norway, Sweden, France, and India are among the ten countries that have invested in artificial intelligence.

CONCLUSIONS

In our opinion, the introduction of mechanisms of joint financing (crowdfunding) of start-up projects in the field of artificial intelligence will significantly increase the possibilities of financing this field.

As we look to a bright future that predicts the well-being of our people through the development of the digital economy, creating the necessary conditions for the introduction of artificial intelligence must be considered as an urgent and priority task of today. If the goals of the digital economy are implemented, great practical results will be evident in all areas, and the well-being of the population will increase significantly.

References:

1. Decision No. 4699 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 28, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of digital economy and electronic government".
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 6079 on approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation.
3. DIGITAL ECONOMY REPORT 2019, VALUE CREATION AND CAPTURE: IMPLICATIONS FOR DEVELOPING COUNTRIES. United Nations Geneva, 2019.– P. 17.
4. Katrashova Yu.V., Mityashin G.Yu. Ispolzovanie "skvoznix" texnologiy v sfere gosudarstvennogo upravleniya, Nauka Krasnoyarya, Tom 9, №4, 2020. – S 88.
5. Jahon Iqtisodiy Forumi va Boston Konsalting Guruhi, Ta'limga yangicha qarash: Texnologiyalar salohiyatini ochish (Jeneva: Jahon Iqtisodiy Forumi, 2015), https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEFUSA_NewVisionforEducation_Report2015.pdf Ruhsat bilan qayta chop etilgan.
6. Stat.uz website
7. Eshmuhammadovna, S. D. (2022). TRENDS AND NEW DEVELOPMENT METHODS IN STATISTICS. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10 (6), 680–686.
8. Сафарова, Д. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ И ОБЛАСТИ СТАТИСТИКИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(5), 171-177.
9. Safarova, D. E. (2023). IMPORTANCE AND PROBLEMS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY IN INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT. Publishing House "Baltija Publishing".
10. Safarova, D. E. (2023). IMPORTANCE AND PROBLEMS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY IN INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT. Publishing House "Baltija Publishing".

11. Safarova, D. E. (2022). Innovative Changes and Tendencies in the Development of Statistics. American Journal of Economics and Business Management, 5(11), 129-135.
12. Azatovna, Y. G., & Ortikalievna, B. M. (2022). The development of social infrastructure as a factor in managing the innovative development of the region. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 65-70.
13. Юлдашева, Г. А. (2023). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ РОЗНИЧНОЙ И ОПТОВОЙ ТОРГОВЛИ С УЧЕТОМ ИНФЛЯЦИИ. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(5), 164-166.
14. Юлдашева, Г. А. (2023). ФИНАНСОВАЯ ОТЧЕТНОСТЬ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ ОПТОВОЙ И РОЗНИЧНОЙ ТОРГОВЛИ В АСПЕКТЕ АВТОМАТИЗАЦИИ. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(5), 167-170.
15. Yuldasheva, G. A. (2022). Modernization of the Accounting System in Accordance with International Requirements. American Journal of Economics and Business Management, 5(11), 146-149.